

Comparison Among Novice Evaluators: Using the Granollers Method and DUXAIT-NG in Remote Heuristic Evaluation

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Abstract. This paper presents a case study using the Granollers method and the digital platform DUXAIT-NG by novice evaluators in remote heuristic evaluations. This study aims to share the results and findings obtained from the evaluators' experience. This case study describes the Remote Usability Evaluation carried out on the redesigned Figma prototype of the website of a public hospital in Peru as part of a redesign project and within the context of a university project to bring students closer to the university's research groups. In this sense, an evaluation team was formed, led by a researcher who acted as a guide, trainer, and facilitator of the whole experience. As part of the case planning, it was decided to perform a Remote Usability Evaluation, use the Granollers method to conduct heuristic evaluations, and perform the whole experience with the DUXAIT-NG platform as a support tool. The novice evaluators used the Granollers heuristic set for the first time, which stands out for its clear structure and practical approach. They also used the DUXAIT-NG platform to record all evaluation stages and visualize the results in a centralized platform. Integrating the method into DUXAIT-NG allowed evaluators to systematically track identified issues, improving organization and reducing common errors associated with traditional tools. The study included three novice evaluators and one evaluator with intermediate experience. The average SUS score for the platform was 81.88, indicating good usability for the platform utilized. Evaluators highlighted that the platform significantly facilitated the evaluation process, as evidenced by the SUS and TAM questionnaires. This study underscores the advantages of using the Granollers method with a digital platform such as DUXAIT-NG for Remote Usability Evaluations, where efficiency and organization are key.

Keywords: Human-Computer Interaction, Heuristic Evaluation, User Experience, Usability, Case Study, Healthcare, Remote Usability Evaluation.

1 Introduction

Heuristic evaluation [1] is one of the most widely used techniques in usability analysis and evaluation [2][3]. It allows for the structured and efficient identification of user interface issues. In this context, the Granollers method emerges as a detailed, structured alternative that expands on traditional heuristic principles [4]. Furthermore, digital tools, such as DUXAIT-NG, have transformed how these evaluations are conducted, optimizing the recording, analysis, and presentation of results, especially in remote settings.

In the field of heuristic evaluation, having well-trained evaluators is essential for effectively identifying usability issues [5]. However, novice evaluators often face challenges in their early experiences, such as interpreting heuristics, identifying and classifying problems, and documenting findings in a structured manner [3]. For this reason, a key aspect of this study is to analyze how evaluators with no prior experience can develop competencies in applying the Granollers method for Heuristic Evaluations and using digital support platforms such as DUXAIT-NG.

In this sense, this case study is proposed from two contexts. In the first context, a thesis project was underway to redesign the web portal of a public hospital in Peru using a user-centered approach, and the project leader

required feedback on her proposal. Therefore, she asked the research group to conduct a usability evaluation of her prototype designed in Figma during the evaluation phase of her project.

In the second context, an internal university project called Re-inventa2 [6], which seeks to bring students of the first semesters closer to the research groups, was underway. In that sense, a group of students without experience in Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and User Experience (UX) evaluation was supported. Therefore, they entered a training and formation process to perform different usability evaluation techniques.

In these two contexts, it was proposed to constitute an evaluation team led by a researcher who would act as a guide, trainer, and facilitator of the whole experience. As part of the case planning, it was decided to perform a Remote Usability Evaluation, use the Granollers method to conduct heuristic evaluations and carry out the whole experience with the DUXAIT-NG platform as a support platform.

This study also aims to compare the performance of novice evaluators with an evaluator who had previously conducted an evaluation using the same method and platform. The objective is to analyze differences in aspects such as the number and type of problems identified, the time spent on the evaluation, and the perceived ease of use of the digital tool. This comparison not only helps measure the impact of prior experience on the effectiveness of Heuristic Evaluation but also identifies which aspects of the process can be optimized to improve the training of new evaluators. By centralizing the process in a structured platform, the study seeks to lower entry barriers for novice evaluators and enhance the quality of their analysis.

The paper is organized as follows: Sections 1 and 2 explain the evaluation method and the platform in detail. Section 3 describes the methods used to conduct the Heuristic Evaluation process and the selection of participants, including the addition of a fourth evaluator with prior experience using the tool and technique to compare performance. Section 4 presents the results, demonstrating how all evaluators completed the task and visualized the outcomes. In the final sections, participants highlighted how the platform significantly facilitated the process, evidenced by tools like the SUS and TAM questionnaires.

2 Background

This section defines the main concepts used in this research.

2.1 Heuristic evaluation

Heuristic evaluation is a widely used usability inspection method for identifying design problems in user interfaces [1]. It consists of evaluating an interface against a set of recognized design principles, known as heuristics. The most influential heuristics were developed by Nielsen and Molich [7] and provide a basis for evaluating the usability of a system. Heuristic evaluation is valued for its efficiency and ability to identify usability problems early in design development, and it applies to every stage in the design and redesign processes. However, the effectiveness of heuristic evaluation is highly dependent on the experience and knowledge of the evaluators [5]. Novice evaluators often face challenges interpreting heuristics, identifying relevant issues, and systematically documenting their findings [5].

2.2 Granollers method for heuristic evaluations

The Granollers method [4] enhances and specifies traditional heuristic principles. It offers a more detailed and organized set of heuristics, making it easier for less experienced evaluators to apply them effectively. Notable for its practical approach, the method systematically guides evaluators throughout the evaluation process. It comprises 15 categories for a thorough and precise user experience analysis. Additionally, the Granollers method facilitates the calculation of a numerical value known as Usability Percentage, which can be utilized for comparisons and various quantitative analyses.

2.3 Digital tools for heuristic evaluations

Digital tools have transformed how usability evaluations are conducted. These tools facilitate the planning, execution, analysis, and presentation of evaluation results. In the context of heuristic evaluation, digital tools provide direct access to heuristics, enable systematic recording of identified issues, foster collaboration between evaluators, and generate automated reports. The DUXAIT-NG platform [8] exemplifies a digital tool designed to support the heuristic evaluation process, particularly in remote settings.

2.4 Usability in the healthcare domain

Applying usability principles in the healthcare domain presents many advantages [9]. However, prior usability evaluations of software products in this domain have uncovered significant issues that adversely affect the user experience, including content quality, information organization and retrieval, visual design, and navigability, among others [10]. Another study similarly emphasized that websites created without a user-centered approach tend to have low usage rates and often lead to user abandonment [11].

In the context of the redesign project that motivates the present heuristic evaluation, it was identified that the original design process lacked a user-centered approach. This deficiency resulted in an interface that, although compliant with legal requirements, did not meet the needs and expectations of the end users.

As indicated in the previous section, a usability evaluation was required to validate the results of a redesign process. Specifically, three aspects were to be covered:

- Identify usability problems
- Evaluate compliance with usability heuristics
- Provide recommendations for redesign

Therefore, the heuristic evaluation detailed in this study was an important step in the redesign process. The goal was to transform an interface focused on legal compliance into one that prioritizes usability and user experience in healthcare.

3 Methods

This section details the methodology followed for the case study.

In general terms, the process followed can be seen in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Process followed.

3.1 Case study design

The page selected for analysis by the evaluators was the redesign proposal for the Hermilio Valdizán Hospital website [12]. As shown in Figure 2, this proposal is presented in the Figma tool and was designed to provide a more efficient and usable user experience, allowing patients to manage various medical services digitally. To achieve this goal, interviews were conducted with the patient's family members, who were the primary users of the hospital's website, to understand the main difficulties and expectations of the target audience.

Based on the information collected, the designer created the prototype for Figma. Its interface enables navigation through different sections, such as information on medical specialties, doctors, consultation hours, and administrative processes. One of the key features is the appointment booking function, which is intended to allow users to select the type of consultation they need, their preferred specialist, and the most convenient available time slot through an interactive calendar option.

The lead of the evaluation team decided to evaluate the prototype using the Granollers heuristic set due to its clear structure and adaptability to different usability evaluation contexts. Unlike more general approaches, such as Nielsen’s heuristics, the Granollers set expands and details heuristic principles, providing 15 categories for a more thorough and specific user experience analysis. Additionally, its formulation facilitates application by evaluators with different experience levels, making it an ideal choice for training novice evaluators.

Another key factor in this choice was integrating this set within the DUXAIT-NG platform, which enabled a more structured and efficient evaluation process, ensuring that evaluators had direct access to the heuristics within the platform without needing external references.

Fig. 2. Screenshot of Figma prototype “Hermilio Valdizán”.

3.2 Participant selection

The evaluation of the Hospital Nacional “Hermilio Valdizán” prototype involved three novice evaluators (Evaluator 1, Evaluator 2, and Evaluator 3), one evaluator (Evaluator 4) with intermediate experience, and a moderator.

The novice evaluators had prior theoretical training in heuristic evaluations and had completed a case study following the formal process proposed by Freddy Paz (5) using Nielsen’s heuristic set [1]. However, they had no previous experience conducting usability evaluations with the Granollers heuristics. Additionally, they had basic skills in using digital tools but had never interacted with the DUXAIT-NG platform for an evaluation before.

The evaluator with intermediate experience had previously participated in evaluations using the Granollers heuristics and had prior experience working with the DUXAIT-NG platform [13].

The moderator had prior experience managing heuristic evaluations and using the DUXAIT-NG tool. In her role, she guided the Granollers heuristics, facilitated the evaluation process, monitored the evaluators’ progress, and addressed their questions during the sessions.

3.3 Evaluation process

The evaluation process consisted of three synchronous sessions and one asynchronous session, in which both the three novice evaluators and the evaluator with intermediate experience participated. Figure 3 shows the scope of each of the four sessions.

Fig. 3. Evaluation sessions.

Profiling and introduction. The first session was conducted to familiarize the new evaluators with applying the Granollers method using the DUXAIT-NG tool (8). Each new evaluator was profiled during this session, and the tool was briefly introduced. Additionally, all evaluators were assigned to the “Granollers Evaluation—Hermilio Valdizán Hospital Prototype” evaluation, as shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Screenshot of the DUXAIT-NG platform of the evaluation.

Platform Use Induction. During the second session, an inspection of each heuristic used in the evaluation was conducted. The evaluation moderator led this inspection to identify any issues or questions regarding the 15 heuristics.

Evaluation. The evaluation process was asynchronous, where each evaluator took a different time on the test, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Evaluation time of each evaluator.

Evaluators	Nº of sessions	Total time
Evaluator 1	1 session	2 hours
Evaluator 2	8 session	3 hours
Evaluator 3	1 session	1 hour
Evaluator 4	1 session	45 min

Results and discussion session. The fourth session was conducted with all evaluators and the moderator to align each evaluator's findings and identify common points.

Additionally, relevant comments were generated regarding the evaluation process, the time allocated for analysis, and the sessions conducted to complete the evaluation.

During the meeting, the following aspects were addressed:

- Experience with the platform: The effectiveness of DUXAIT-NG for the evaluation was discussed, focusing on navigation, accessibility, and understanding of the website prototype’s design.
- Evaluation methodology: The evaluation criteria were assessed, considering whether the measurement variables were appropriate and whether DUXAIT-NG allowed for a fair and structured evaluation.
- Suggestions for improvement: To optimize future evaluations, recommendations were made, and improvements were proposed for the Hermilio Valdizán prototype.
- Perceived value: The usefulness and relevance of the process were highlighted, emphasizing the evaluation's impact and contribution to the continuous improvement of future systems to be analyzed.

3.4 Data analysis

Table 2 shows the usability rating assigned by each evaluator individually and asynchronously based on their responses to each heuristic.

Table 2. Results of evaluation 1.

#	Heuristics	Eval. 1	Eval. 2	Eval. 3	Eval. 4
1	Visibility and system state	4.75/5.00	2.50/3.00	4.50/5.00	5.00/5.00
2	Connection between the system and the real world, metaphor usage and human objects	2.75/4.00	3.50/4.00	3.75/4.00	4.00/4.00
3	User control and freedom	1.00/2.00	1.25/3.00	1.50/2.00	2.50/3.00
4	Consistency and standards	5.00/6.00	3.50/5.00	4.50/5.00	6.00/6.00
5	Recognition rather than memory, learning and anticipation	3.25/5.00	2.75/3.00	3.75/4.00	4.25/5.00
6	Flexibility and efficiency of use	0.75/1.00	0.00/0.00	1.25/2.00	2.00/2.00
7	Help users recognize, diagnose and recover from errors	0.00/0.00	0.00/0.00	0.00/0.00	0.00/0.00
8	Preventing errors	0.00/0.00	0.25/1.00	0.75/1.00	2.00/2.00
9	Aesthetic and minimalist design	2.00/4.00	2.50/4.00	3.50/4.00	4.00/4.00
10	Help and documentation	1.00/1.00	2.00/2.00	3.50/4.00	0.00/0.00
11	Save the state and protect the work	0.00/0.00	0.00/0.00	0.75/1.00	0.00/0.00
12	Color and readability	3.00/3.00	3.00/4.00	3.00/3.00	3.00/3.00
13	Autonomy	0.00/0.00	0.00/0.00	3.00/3.00	2.00/2.00
14	Defaults	0.00/0.00	0.00/0.00	0.00/0.00	0.00/0.00
15	Latency reduction	0.00/0.00	0.50/1.00	0.75/1.00	0.00/0.00

Notable usability results were obtained in the website's evaluation using the Granollers method on the DUXAIT-NG platform. However, as Table 3 shows, there was some variability among the four evaluators.

Table 3. Comparison of usability scores among evaluators.

Evaluators	Total score	Answered questions that count (without not applicable)	Usability percentage
Evaluator 1	23.50	31	61.99%
Evaluator 2	21.75	30	57.24%
Evaluator 3	34.50	39	63.37%
Evaluator 4	32.75	34	71.66%

The data suggests a generally favorable perception of the website's usability, although slight differences between evaluators were identified. These variations may be attributed to personal criteria or specific interpretations of the heuristics.

The usability study conducted by the four evaluators reflects an overall percentage of 64.06%, indicating that the website meets usability principles at a moderate level. However, there are still areas for improvement. DUXAIT-NG generates a summary table with the data already averaged by each evaluator, as shown in Figure 5. The table in that figure presents the values obtained for the 15 evaluated heuristics. Some heuristics stand out due to their relatively high scores, such as HG04 (4.75/5.50) and HG01 (4.19/4.50). However, certain heuristics have considerably low values, such as HG07 (0.00/1.75), HG08 (0.25/1.00), and HG14 (0.00/0.25), highlighting critical areas that require improvement.

Some positive usability aspects observed in the prototype are as follows:

- The heuristics address essential aspects such as system status visibility, ensuring that users receive clear messages about their actions, such as scheduling an appointment or submitting a form.
- The system-world correspondence is maintained using clear and understandable language, avoiding unnecessary technical terms.
- The prototype ensures user control and freedom by providing options to cancel or undo actions.
- The interface adheres to standards using familiar icons and design patterns, facilitating comprehension.
- Cognitive load is reduced through dropdown menus and intuitive icons, promoting recognition over recall.
- The aesthetic and minimalist design highlights key information while avoiding unnecessary elements.
- Error tolerance allows users to edit data before submission.

Fig. 5. Screenshot of the evaluation results in the platform.

These results were returned to the redesign project leader, who had very positive feedback regarding the findings and executed a new iteration in the context of her project with the reported findings.

4 Results

This section details the main results and findings after the heuristic evaluation. Delivering these results is part of the methodological process indicated in the previous section.

4.1 Performance of novice evaluators

The novice evaluators learned how to use the DUXAIT-NG platform with their mentor before starting the evaluation in Session 1. They learned how to register, initiate an evaluation, and explore the platform’s benefits, such as the ability to track each evaluator’s progress online. Despite using this tool for the first time, the evaluators demonstrated a good understanding of how to interact with it. Thanks to the platform’s features, the moderator could monitor the evaluators’ progress, notify them of any incomplete steps, and check for potential difficulties.

During this evaluation, the heuristic related to latency reduction was excluded, as it could not be assessed within the prototype page.

On average, the evaluators used the platform for two hours, and no significant difficulties were reported in completing the evaluation, which the evaluators appreciated.

Upon completing the evaluation, each evaluator used the tool to visualize the results provided by the platform, which included detailed graphs and comments from all evaluators. These results allowed evaluators to generate a more straightforward and thorough report. They highlighted this functionality as highly useful for clients receiving the evaluation results and evaluators compiling their reports.

4.2 Comparison among evaluators

Table 4 shows differences in evaluator performance based on experience level, time spent, and the number of heuristics applied. These data help identify trends and patterns in how evaluators approached the analysis of the DUXAIT platform.

Table 4. Comparison among evaluators.

Evaluators	Level of Expertise	Usability percentage	Number of Applied Heuristics	Total time
Evaluator 1	Novice	61.99%	9	2 hours
Evaluator 2	Novice	57.24%	10	3 hours
Evaluator 3	Novice	63.37%	13	1 hour
Evaluator 4	Medium	71.66%	10	45 min

Evaluator 4, with medium expertise, completed the evaluation in 45 minutes, whereas the novice evaluators required between 1 and 3 hours for the same process. This difference suggests that experience plays a key role in evaluation efficiency, allowing for faster analysis without compromising the number of applied heuristics.

Among the novices, Evaluator 2 spent the most time (3 hours), which aligns with their strategy of dividing the evaluation into multiple sessions and conducting a prior inspection of the prototype. In contrast, Evaluator

3 completed the evaluation in 1 hour, applying 13 heuristics, the highest among all evaluators. This indicates that some novice evaluators conducted a more extensive analysis in less time, possibly due to greater familiarity with the platform or a more agile evaluation approach.

The number of heuristics applied varied among evaluators, with Evaluator 3 identifying 13, while Evaluator 1 reported only 9. Despite using more heuristics, Evaluator 3 obtained a usability percentage of 63.37%, a figure close to Evaluator 1 (61.99%). This suggests that a higher number of applied heuristics does not necessarily translate into a higher usability percentage, as it depends on each evaluator’s perception and interpretation of heuristics.

Evaluator 4, with medium expertise, achieved the highest usability percentage (71.66%). This indicates that their evaluation may have been more favorable toward the prototype than novice evaluators, who were more critical in their analysis.

4.3 Evaluation strategies and their impact on results

Evaluator 2 mentioned inspecting the prototype before starting the evaluation, which may have influenced their perception and the total time spent. However, their usability percentage was the lowest (57.24%), suggesting that their analysis was more critical than that of other evaluators.

On the other hand, Evaluator 3 used a faster evaluation strategy and applied more heuristics in less time, which could indicate a more efficient analysis. Nevertheless, their usability percentage was similar to that of Evaluator 1, implying that a quicker evaluation does not always result in significantly different outcomes.

Evaluator 4, with more experience, conducted the evaluation progressively and synchronously, allowing him to identify issues online and respond more directly. This efficient approach enabled him to complete the evaluation quickly while achieving the highest usability percentage.

4.4 Opinions and impact of the DUXAIT-NG tool

At the end of the evaluation process, the evaluators were asked to complete a SUS questionnaire [14], a Total Average Mean questionnaire [15], and their final comments on the DUXAIT-NG platform to provide a comprehensive understanding of the system’s performance across different evaluators, shedding light on areas of strength as well as opportunities for improvement. Table 5 shows the results.

The System Usability Scale results showed an average score of 81.88, which indicates a generally good usability level for the system. A SUS score above 68 is typically considered above average, with higher scores reflecting better-perceived usability. Overall, the SUS results indicate that most evaluators deem the system highly usable, with a minor outlier (Evaluator 2) indicating room for improvement.

The TAM score, which provides insight into the overall user experience, yielded an average score of 5.51 out of 7. This suggests that, on average, the evaluators had a positive experience with the system, though there is still room for enhancement. The individual TAM results were as follows: While the TAM scores are generally favorable, the variation in individual results (particularly Evaluator 2) highlights potential issues or inconsistencies in the user experience that may require further investigation.

Table 5. TAM questionnaire results.

Evaluator	System Usability Scale (SUS) results	Total Average Mean (TAM) Results
Evaluator 1	87.5	138
Evaluator 2	67.5	108

Evaluator 3	80.0	143
Evaluator 4	92.5	136
Total Result	81.88	(529/96) = 5.51

While the system is generally well-received, the lower SUS score from Evaluator 2 suggests the presence of specific usability challenges. This may warrant further examination to identify potential pain points or usability issues, especially if similar feedback is found in a more extensive user sample.

In their final comments, the evaluators highlighted several benefits of the DUXAIT-NG platform. The platform was much easier to use due to the simplicity of completing the forms. These were well-organized by heuristics, and each question targeted a specific feature of the digital product’s usability. This aspect was helpful since it was challenging during the first evaluation to formulate questions that would help identify usability issues in accordance with the heuristics.

On the platform, visual evidence in photos or screenshots was unnecessary, which some evaluators considered an advantage for streamlining the process. However, this also led to more detailed and complex descriptions that could still be understood without visual evidence.

5 Discussion

This study's findings highlight key aspects of the heuristic evaluation process using the Granollers method and the DUXAIT-NG platform. Several observations emerge from the results, particularly regarding evaluator performance, evaluation efficiency, and platform usability.

One of the main insights is the relationship between experience and evaluation efficiency. The more experienced evaluator completed the task significantly faster while still identifying comparable usability issues. This suggests that training and familiarity with heuristic evaluation methodologies can be crucial in optimizing the evaluation process.

Regarding the application of heuristics, the results indicate that a higher number of heuristics applied does not necessarily correlate with a higher usability percentage. This suggests that some evaluators may have been more critical in their assessments, leading to a more conservative usability rating. This raises an interesting question about how subjective factors influence heuristic evaluation outcomes.

Additionally, the TAM and SUS scores suggest that the DUXAIT-NG platform is generally well-received in terms of usability, but with some areas requiring improvement. The main usability issues were related to aspects such as error prevention and system feedback, which could be refined in future platform iterations.

Finally, while novice evaluators faced initial challenges, they completed the evaluation successfully, highlighting the potential of structured digital tools to facilitate the learning process. This aligns with the broader goal of improving UX evaluation methodologies by integrating digital support tools.

5.1 Limitations of the study

This study has some limitations that should be considered. The sample size was relatively small, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. In addition, the study focused on a specific context (the evaluation of a prototype hospital website), which may also limit the generalizability of the results to other types of systems or contexts.

5.2 Implications for novice evaluator training

The findings of this study have several implications for the training of novice evaluators. First, the results suggest that using structured methods and digital tools can facilitate the learning process and improve the performance of novice evaluators. Second, the results highlight the importance of experience in evaluation efficiency, suggesting that training should focus on providing novice evaluators with opportunities to practice and develop their skills.

6 Conclusions and future works

The results of this study underscore the importance of relying on structured digital tools for heuristic evaluation processes, especially for novice evaluators. The novice evaluators' lack of experience was mitigated using the Granollers method with DUXAIT-NG. This integration effectively streamlined the evaluation workflow and ensured a structured approach to usability evaluation.

Some additional findings that emerge from this study are as follows:

- Experience influences efficiency: More experienced evaluators completed the evaluation in less time and perceived usability more favorably.
- More applied heuristics do not always result in higher usability scores: Interpretation and judgment play a crucial role.
- Evaluation strategies vary: Some evaluators preferred a detailed initial analysis, while others conducted the evaluation progressively.
- Novice evaluators tend to be more critical: This could be due to stricter heuristic interpretation or a lack of familiarity with usability evaluation processes.

These findings provide valuable insights for enhancing future evaluations. Expanding the participant pool to include a more extensive and more diverse group of evaluators would help validate the results and identify broader usability patterns. Additionally, optimizing the training process for evaluators in heuristic inspections and developing more efficient strategies for utilizing the DUXAIT-NG platform could further improve the accuracy and effectiveness of usability assessments.

As for future work, there are two lines of work in the roadmap for the platform's evolution: the first is to continue carrying out new usability evaluations in other contexts, in other domains, and with other work teams with different profiles. The second line of work is the implementation of new modules that support other evaluation methods and techniques, as well as exploring AI techniques to further automate and digitize the user experience evaluation processes.

Finally, future research could address this study's limitations and expand its findings. For example, future studies could include larger sample sizes and examine the use of the Granollers method and the DUXAIT-NG platform in different contexts. In addition, future research could explore strategies to improve the training of novice raters and analyze the impact of different types of training on their performance.

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